

ONE OF THE FUTURE TASKS OF DEVELOPING INTERETHNIC RELATIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article analyzed the issues of developing interethnic relations in the new Uzbekistan.

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In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the extensive reforms in the field of interethnic relations, the study of the national composition of the population, and the activities of national cultural centers are among the pressing issues of today. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PF-158, dated September 11, 2023, "On the Strategy 'Uzbekistan - 2030'," as well as the principle of "a safe and peace-loving state" outlined in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the defined priority tasks serve as a methodological basis for every researcher today. These ideas determine the relevance of the issue we are studying and require the disclosure of the unique national characteristics of each ethnic group. Currently, the majority of countries in the world are multi-ethnic. It is noteworthy that the Republic of Uzbekistan is also among such countries, and this does not hinder the maintenance of peace and harmony among its citizens. World experience shows that the stability of a state largely depends on its ability to resolve various problems in interethnic relations. In recent times, in the context of increasing global conflicts, including interethnic disputes, this issue has become particularly important. In this regard, interethnic harmony is a decisive factor for any multi-ethnic state. Today, the foundation of the prosperity and development of all states undoubtedly lies in the peaceful and prosperous life of various ethnic and cultural groups, stable mutual relations, and tolerance. In the country, having a positive attitude towards the cultures of other ethnic groups, respecting their national values and traditions, preserving their cultural heritage, and passing it on to future generations is the duty of every citizen. Our first President, I. Karimov, said, "...Another important task is to assist in the development of the language, culture, customs, and traditions of all ethnic groups living in Uzbekistan, and to further expand the opportunities and conditions created for them. Through this, preserving the interethnic harmony and stability established in our country, cherishing it like the apple of our eye, is the sacred duty of each of us." Intercultural dialogue provides the opportunity to participate in relations at all

levels. Nevertheless, some aspects of it have not been fully illuminated. In today's information age, where our consciousness is being captured to an unimaginable extent, it is not wrong to consider the rapid growth of cultural integration among peoples as a natural process. At the same time, in the era of globalization, the issue of preserving national identity remains a pressing concern for peoples who hold a special place in the history of great material and non-material cultures and world civilizations. The social existence created by humans, the surrounding environment, and artifacts are the products of their consciousness and intellect. The object, as Hegel said, "exists for itself," but the force that turns this object into an artifact is human consciousness and thought. The relationships between people are also influenced by subjective factors—consciousness, intellect, and ideological influences. In our daily lives, searching for ethnopsychological traits in the person sitting next to us has become so ingrained in our consciousness that we unconsciously engage in racial discrimination, distinguishing "Them" from "Us" or "Me" without fully realizing it. True, this is not yet ethno-egoism, but if some external cause arises, the force in our consciousness that seeks differences immediately comes into play. Understanding national unity and solidarity can only be based on a comprehended national idea. In this sense, we can agree with the Ukrainian philosopher S. Krymsky, who said, "An ethnos without its own statehood cannot pass through a period of free development." Interethnic relations do not arise outside of consciousness and intellect. Actions and statements like "Yours"- "Mine" have an objective character, but they are the products of ethnopsychological perceptions formed in the consciousness. Therefore, the formation and development of interethnic relations are also based on ideological and spiritual foundations. Interethnic relations are one of the most delicate and complex socio-political issues in every country in the world, each with its own history and characteristics. In particular, the national issue is one of the influential factors shaping the concept of national security in states, and the fact that some states cannot find a solution to these issues is becoming a factor damaging national security. It is no secret that the lack of harmony in interethnic relations not only harms the internal political stability and national security of individual states but also of entire regions. The love and loyalty of all ethnic groups living in Uzbekistan to the homeland, formed on the basis of "Uzbekistan is our common home," can be understood from the results of surveys conducted. Sociological surveys show that the attitude of our citizens towards being citizens of Uzbekistan varies. In 2008, 50.7% of respondents considered both ethnicity

and citizenship important, and in 2010, this figure rose to 58.1%. Among Karakalpaks, 23.9% considered ethnicity important, while 10.9% considered citizenship important; among Kazakhs, these figures were 27.3% and 18.2%, respectively; among Kyrgyz, 11.1% and 5.6%; among Slavs, in 2006, 25.6% and 16.3%, and in 2010, 23.1% and 7.7%. In general, the pride in being a citizen of Uzbekistan among representatives of various ethnic groups has been increasing year by year. In 2003, it was 68.5%, in 2006—68.7%, in 2007—68.4%, in 2008—62.1%, in 2010—76.8%, and in 2013—84.1%. In the 2013 survey, 96.0% of Tajiks, 89.5% of Turkmens, 85.2% of Uzbeks, 83.3% of Kazakhs, and every second Slav expressed pride in being citizens of Uzbekistan. In the regional distribution, the percentage of respondents who expressed pride in being citizens of Uzbekistan in 2013 was 100% in Surkhandarya, 96.3% in Syrdarya, 94.9% in Khorezm, 93.9% in Kashkadarya, 92.9% in Jizzakh, 90.9% in Fergana, 89.4% in Bukhara, 86.4% in Namangan, 85.3% in Navoiy, and 83.5% in Tashkent city. Thus, the direction in which national ideology should be promoted is clear from these figures. According to national ideology, citizens should consider Uzbekistan their homeland, work for its future, strive, seek, and live as their own country. The main mechanism for instilling national ideology into the consciousness of the younger generation is education. If national ideology is instilled into the consciousness of the younger generation through ethno-cultural education, the worst habit of distinguishing between "Me" and "You" will not arise among ethnic groups. If national ideology serves the state based on the principle of society-humanity, then looking at other ethnic groups in society with a nationalist perspective will not be for the titular ethnic group. Conflicts in interethnic relations and nationalism can completely disrupt the social life of countries, even leading to the fragmentation of some states. As a result, social stability in an entire region can be disrupted. In October 1995, the French living in Quebec, Canada, although not a majority, sought to give their native language the status of a state language and to secede from Canada through a referendum. Other ethnic groups did not support this, but the actions aimed at secession continued. A similar process was observed in the Karakalpakstan Republic on July 2-3, 2022, where attempts were made to achieve independence through a referendum. Of course, external forces had an influence here. Because something or someone prompted the crowd to take to the streets. Considering the polyethnic nature of most countries in the world, we understand that the concept of "citizen" is higher than the concept of "ethnicity," and it is important to awaken love for the homeland in people's hearts. In multi-ethnic Uzbekistan,

the sharpness in interethnic relations has been decreasing year by year, and friendship, harmony, and mutual trust among them have been increasing. This can be explained by the correct direction of the ethnic policy being pursued in our country and the tolerant attitude of the Uzbek people towards people of other religions and ethnicities. During the Soviet era, the term "small ethnic group" was widely used and was used to demean other ethnic groups. Naturally, this situation was perceived as an insult and discrimination by other ethnic groups. The new ethno-political paradigm has abandoned such an approach to national issues. In our country, the term "small ethnic group" is not used, as the Uzbek people do not want to demean the status of other peoples and ethnic groups living together. In the 21st century, humanity has faced global economic, social, political, ecological, and ideological problems. The construction of a secular and democratic society in our country and its unique characteristics require foreseeing various ideological threats to the youth, determining the counter-effects of these threats, and developing an immune system against them. Ideological threats are aimed at undermining the integrity and sovereignty of states, overthrowing the political system from within. In most cases, ethnic conflicts are also provoked. "In fact, the threats to security are quite diverse. They include political extremism, including religious extremism, nationalism and national limitations, ethnic, interethnic, local, and tribal conflicts, corruption and crime, and environmental problems. In other words, the threats mentioned above, although manifested differently in different regions, must cause concern in humanity in the same way." With the end of the "Cold War," the formation of a new world order in the system of international relations began. This process is intensifying through globalization and integration. It is known that globalization is an objective and lawful process, and it has both positive and negative characteristics. Globalization allows states to enter the international arena, cooperate with desired states, and integrate to meet national interests. On the other hand, it leads to conflicts on the geopolitical field of powerful states, the establishment of control over weak and newly developing states, and the application of various pressures on independent states. The idea of creating a "global government" under the banner of Americanism is being promoted. The efforts of developing countries to form their own national statehood are not sincerely evaluated by Western experts. For example, Z. Brzezinski writes that as a result of reforms in Russia, totalitarianism has disappeared, but elements of authoritarianism still exist. The democratic reform process in the states of the former Union is viewed with

suspicion, and all positive changes are negatively and falsely evaluated as "stagnation," "state oppression," "the absence and impossibility of building a civil society," "the absence of changes," and "the violation of human rights." Similar thoughts are used to include states that have chosen the path of independent development in "special lists" as "lost states," and on this basis, measures to export democracy to them are considered. However, "in state-building, there are no ready-made molds and standards that can be accepted without critical consideration. There are no two exactly identical states in the world. This cannot be. Each state is a unique social phenomenon. It is the product of the historical and spiritual development of each people, the result of the development of its own unique culture." The Uzbek nation, like other peoples living in the region, has gone through complex ethno-historical, socio-cultural, and political processes, and has demonstrated its unifying potential among the peoples of the region in the turbulent periods of history. Today, the "Strategy of Actions" and the program tasks within its framework are aimed at further strengthening the ethno-social and political unity of Uzbekistan, as well as ensuring regional socio-cultural development on the basis of good neighborliness and beneficial cooperation among the region's population, and elevating the tradition of loyalty to centuries-old friendship and kinship ties, which is considered one of the main aspects of Uzbekistan's state policy and is a phenomenological feature. Because today, the reforms being carried out by our state are based on humanistic ideas. Because the equality of every ethnic group living in Uzbekistan before the law is legally guaranteed. In recent years, one of the priority directions of state policy has been to ensure interethnic harmony and tolerance in society, strengthen the atmosphere of friendship and the feeling of a large multi-ethnic family, educate the youth in the spirit of love and loyalty to the homeland, respect for national and universal values, and expand cultural and educational ties with foreign countries.

References:

1. Конрад Н.И. Запад и Восток. – М.: Наука, 1972. – С. 17.
2. Бромлей Ю. Этносоциальные процессы: теория, история, современность. – М: Наука, 1987. – с.333; Винер Б. Е.Этничность: в поисках парадигмы изучения//Этнографическое обозрение.1998.-№4.-с 20-32. Shaw M.Graur Dynamics.-New York, 1995.r.13-15.
3. Тишков В. Этничность, национализм и государство в посткоммунистическом обществе//Вопросы социологии. Москва: 1993.№1.-С.4.

4. Барт Р. Избранные работы: семиотика. Поэтика. -Москва.: Мысль,1989.-С.28-42.; Jackson R.Ethicity.In Social science concerts: A systematic analysis,Ed.byg.Sartory.Beverly Hills.-London,1984.-r.24-26.
5. Широкогоров С. Этнос. Исследование основных принципов изменения этнических и этнографических явлений // Известия восточного факультета Дальневосточного университета. Т.1. – Шанхай, 1923. – С. 13.
6. Бромлей Ю. Очерки теории этноса. - М.: Наука, 1983.– С. 34.
7. Asqarov A. O'zbek xalqi etnogenez va etnik tarixining ba'zi bir nazariy va ilmiy metodologik asoslari//Ozbekiston tarixi 2002. №4. 54–60-betlar
8. Шониёзов К. Ўзбек халқининг шаклланиш жараёни.– Т., 2001. – 86 б.
9. Марказий Осиёда анъанавий ва замонавий этномаданий жараёнлар. 1-қисм: Тошкент., 2005.

